

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

D7.5 Report on the InTheMED Final Scientific Conference

VERSION 1.0

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Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

The Deliverable 7.5 reports on the Final Scientific Conference of the InTheMED project that took place at the EGU (European Geosciences Union) General Assembly 2023 in Vienna (Austria) from April 23rd to April 28th, 2023. The final conference was held on the last day, where there was the opportunity for the partners to present their results regarding their technical results obtained under the project framework.

1. Introduction

The InTheMED final conference was organized during the EGU (European Geosciences Union) General Assembly 2023 at the Vienna International Centre (Austria) from April 23rd to April 28th, 2023. This report summarizing this event is part of one of the deliverables of the project (D7.5). All partners attended the event and had the opportunity to present and summarize the progress of each Work Package (WP) in which they are participating, followed by a period of discussion regarding the completion of the final tasks by the end of the project on August 31st, 2023.

The InTheMED final scientific conference happened on April 28th, as part of the EGU program in a session entitled “HS8.1.9 - Sustainable Groundwater Management in Water Stressed Regions”, under the Hydrological Science (HS) program group. The session comprises oral and poster communications.

All partners presented the outcomes of the research activities developed under the scope of the project. Additionally, three invited guests presented during the oral presentation session. Each solicited talk occurred at the beginning of each sub-session. The first talk was given by David Hyndman from the University of Texas at Dallas on “Using Remote Sensing and Integrated Hydrologic Models to Characterize How Irrigated Agriculture Affects Highly Overdrawn Aquifers in the United States”. The second, in the afternoon session, was given by James Butler from the Kansas Geological Survey about “Extending aquifer lifespans with pumping reductions: Experiences from the High Plains aquifer”. And the third and final speaker was Marx Andreas from UFZ that give a talk on “Development of a national-scale decision support system for the water sector in Germany”.

In total, there were 24 oral presentations and 15 poster presentations, of which 10 and 4 were outcomes from InTheMED project, respectively.

2. Final Scientific Conference

This chapter summarizes the final scientific conference referring to the main topics of each presentation. An average of 30 people attended all the oral presentations.

2.1. Agenda

The outline of the InTheMED final conference agenda is shown below. All times refer to CEST.

April 28th, 2023 @ 08:30 – 17:40 · EGU session HS8.1.9 “Sustainable Groundwater Management in Water Stressed Regions” *

08:30 Posters on site and virtual

10:15 Coffee break

10:45 Convener introduction, Jaime Gómez-Hernández

10:50 Orals first sub-session: *Machine learning, inverse modeling and geostatistics* |
Chairpersons: Vanessa A. Godoy, George Karatzas

12:30 Lunch

14:00 Orals second sub-session: *Modeling* | Chairpersons: Maria Giovanna Tanda, Seifeddine Jomaa

15:35 Coffee break

16:15 Orals third sub-session: *Groundwater management* | Chairperson: Jaime Gómez-Hernández

17:40 Closure

*For the **detailed agenda**, please consult the annexes.

2.3. EGU session HS8.1.9 “Sustainable Groundwater Management in Water Stressed Regions”

The InTheMED final scientific conference took place on April 28th, 2023, was allocated to posters and oral presentations under the EGU session HS8.1.9 “Sustainable Groundwater Management in Water Stressed Regions” from InTheMED partners and external presenters.

The session started with the poster session in the morning, where the presenters had the opportunity to share their work and have fruitful discussions between the partners and also with the overall participants of the EGU 2023 conference.

The second part of the session was dedicated to the oral presentations, which were divided into three sub-sessions: 1) Machine learning, inverse modelling and geostatistics; 2) Modelling and 3) Groundwater management. The beginning of each sub-section was marked by a 20-minute talk by invited guests to introduce each topic.

This session was an excellent opportunity to disseminate the project among the EGU 20223 participants and communicate the results from the project to all the partners but also let people know better the InTheMED. It was also a space to explore collaboration opportunities.

Both sessions held presentations on-site and virtually.

2.3.1. Posters on Site and Virtual

The posters session was held during the morning with a total of 15 posters, 4 of them under the InTheMED project. **Table 1** lists all the references, highlighting the posters presented under the InTheMED project.

Table 1. Summary of the poster’s session with references for the abstracts, highlighting the ones presented under the InTheMED project.

#	Posters	Under InTheMED Project?
1	Delfini, I., Chahoud, A., Montanari, A., and Zamrsky, D. (2023): Artificial groundwater recharge for adapting to drought risk in large agricultural areas, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-749. https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-749	No

#	Posters	Under InTheMED Project?
2	Agossou, A., Lee, J.-B., and Yang, J.-S. (2023): Groundwater recharge restoration in urban area using Low Impact Development/Best Practices, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-1980. https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-1980	No
3	Das, S. S., Saraf, A. K., and Goswami, A. (2023): Identification of groundwater recharge zones using comparative analysis of drainage networks, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-16268. https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-16268	No
4	Reimann, T., Genzel, M., Aldarir, A., Fichtner, T., Kavousi, A., Hartmann, A., Grischek, T., and Gräber, P.-W. (2023): Feasibility and application of managed aquifer recharge for a safe and sustainable water supply in Syria, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-16328. https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-16328	No
5	Fagandini, C., Todaro, V., Tanda, M. G., Pereira, J. L., Azevedo, L., and Zanini, A. (2023): Evaluation of three Gap-Filling techniques for daily rainfall data sets: a case study in Portugal, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-1410. https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-1410	Yes
6	Wang, Z., Shu, L., Yin, X., Chen, Y., Niu, S., and Xu, P. (2023): Land use changes- the Remaining Available Aquifer Storage (RAAS) response in arid-semiarid regions: the Baicheng case study, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-1432. https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-1432	No
7	Tanda, M. G., Akrouf, H., Secci, D., Todaro, V., Zanini, A., D'oria, M., Baccouche, H., Mansouri, I., Mellah, T., and Ghrabi, A. (2023): Evaluation of the impact of climate change on the shallow aquifer of Grombalia (Tunisia), EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-4402. https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-4402	Yes
8	Pla, C., Valdes-Abellan, J., Navarro-Hernandez, M. I., Guardiola-Albert, C., Ezquerro, P., Bru, G., Elçi, A., Meisina, C., and Tomas, R. (2023): Multicriteria decision-making approach as a strategy to deal with land subsidence in affected areas, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-11516. https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-11516	No
9	Guardiola-Albert, C., De Stefano, L., and Barracaldo Orrego, J. C. (2023): Standardized piezometric indicator to improve the evaluation of the aquifer state. Doñana case study (SW Spain), EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-5217. https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-5217	No

#	Posters	Under InTheMED Project?
10	Rodrigo-Illarri, J., Rodrigo-Clavero, M.-E., and Romero-Hernández, C.-P. (2023): Effects over infrastructures induced by abnormally high water levels due to the change of irrigation techniques: the case of the Liria-Casinos aquifer (Spain), EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-9087. https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-9087	No
11	A. Godoy, V. and Gómez-Hernández, J. (2023): Pumping strategies towards sustainable use in a stressed aquifer: A case study at the Eastern Mancha Aquifer (Spain), EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-5924. https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-5924	Yes
12	Liu, S., Zhou, Y., Eiman, F., McClain, M., and Wang, X.-S. (2023): Achieving Sustainable Groundwater Development with Effective Measures in Beijing Plain, China, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-6556. https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-6556	No
13	Marazuela, M. Á., García-Gil, A., Baquedano, C., Martínez-León, J., Cruz-Pérez, N., and Santamarta, J. C. (2023): Stormwater management in volcanic islands using dry gallery infiltration systems, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-9282. https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-9282	No
14	Jomaa, S., Chavez, R., Ben-Salem, N., Varouchakis, E., K. Copty, N., P. Karatzas, G., Rode, M., and Gómez-Hernández, J. J. (2023): Power of groundwater data sharing in the Mediterranean region, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-13827. https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-13827	Yes
15	Oláh, S., Szijártó, M., Visnovitz, F., and Mádl-Szőnyi, J. (2023): Geophysical survey of near-surface aquifers for the goals of Managed Aquifer Recharge in a settlement of the Danube-Tisza Interfluve, Hungary, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-12862. https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-12862	No

2.3.2. Orals First Sub-Session: Machine Learning, Inverse Modelling and Geostatistics

The first sub-session was dedicated to machine learning, inverse modelling and geostatistics and was held during the morning, after the poster session, with a total of 9 oral presentations, 6 of them under the InTheMED project. The invited guest, David Hyndman from the University

of Texas at Dallas, introduced the topic with the presentation on “Using Remote Sensing and Integrated Hydrologic Models to Characterize How Irrigated Agriculture Affects Highly Overdrawn Aquifers in the United States”.

Table 2. Summary of the orals first sub-session on “Machine learning, inverse modelling and geostatistics” with references for the abstracts, highlighting the ones presented under the InTheMED project

#	Oral Presentations	Under InTheMED Project?
1	Hyndman, D., Kendall, A., Partridge, T., Stid, J., and Zwickle, A. (2023): Using Remote Sensing and Integrated Hydrologic Models to Characterize the How Irrigated Agriculture Affects Highly Overdrawn Aquifers in the United States, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-17218, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-17218	No
2	Secci, D., Todaro, V., Yologlu, O. C., Copty, N. K., Daloglu Çetinkaya, I., D’Oria, M., Saysel, A. K., Tanda, M. G., and Zanini, A. (2023): An artificial neural network as a quick tool to assess the effects of climate change and agricultural policies on groundwater resources, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-5801, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-5801	Yes
3	Li, Y., Zoccarato, C., Tamellini, L., Piazzola, C., Ezquerro, P., Bru, G., Guardiola-Albert, C., Boni, R., and Teatini, P. (2023): Surrogate-based Bayesian characterization of porous and deformable aquifer systems in water stressed regions, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-8761, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-8761	No
4	Rouhani, A., D’Oria, M., Gómez-Hernández, J. J., Rode, M., and Jomaa, S. (2023): Impact of climate change on groundwater levels in the Iberian Peninsula, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-12968, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-12968	Yes
5	Uribe-Asarta, J., A. Godoy, V., and Gómez-Hernández, J. J. (2023): Random Forests-Based Surrogate Model as a Tool to Facilitate Groundwater Management, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-13470, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-13470	Yes
6	Ojha, M. (2023): Demarcation of lowered water table zones in a drought-affected area of western Odisha, India, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-3742, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-3742	No

#	Oral Presentations	Under InTheMED Project?
7	Escada, C. and Azevedo, L.: Deep Direct Current Resistivity Inversion, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-299, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-299	Yes
8	Azevedo, L. and L. Pereira, J. (2023): Deep generative inversion of ERT data for electrical resistivity, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-15753, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-15753	Yes
9	Panagiotou, C. F., Akrouf, H., Baccouche, H., Mellah, T., Mansouri, L., and Ghrabi, A. (2023): Assessment of groundwater quality and piezometric levels using geostatistical methods in Grombalia aquifer, Tunisia., EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-8037, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-8037 .	Yes

2.3.3. Orals Second Sub-Session: Modelling

The second sub-session was held during the afternoon with the topic Modelling and it began with the presentation by James Butler from Kansas Geological Survey, on “Extending Aquifer Lifespans with Pumping Reductions: Experiences from the High Plains Aquifer”, and counted a total of 8 presentations.

Table 3. Summary of the second sub-session on “Modelling” with references for the abstracts, highlighting the ones presented under the InTheMED project.

#	Oral Presentations	Under InTheMED Project?
1	Butler, J. (2023): Extending aquifer lifespans with pumping reductions: Experiences from the High Plains aquifer, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-9552, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-9552 .	No
2	Genzel, M., Reimann, T., Kavousi Heydari, A., Hartmann, A., Doummar, J., and Rudolph, M.-G. (2023): Regional-scale groundwater modeling, focusing on boundary inflow and impact assessment of managed aquifer recharge in karst systems, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-16393, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-16393 .	No

#	Oral Presentations	Under InTheMED Project?
3	Eryilmaz Saylan, C., Elci, A., and Somay Altas, M. (2023): A Groundwater Flow Modeling Application for the Impact Assessment of Treated Wastewater Reuse by Managed Aquifer Recharge, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-13121, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-13121 .	No
4	Klammler, H., Araújo da Silva Leão, C., Bastos Leal, L. R., and Hatfield, K. (2023): Simplified integrated modeling and potential groundwater management benefits of the unsaturated zone in the Urucuia aquifer system, Brazil, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-4229, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-4229 .	No
5	Patil, Y. and Landage, A. (2023): Evaluation of the Semi-Arid Region Groundwater Storage Potential for Solapur Region, Maharashtra, India, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-4199, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-4199 .	No
6	Dass, B. and Sen, S. (2023): Understanding spring aquifer dynamics through observational data patterns, stable isotopes, and hydrochemistry – An account of experimental pilots in the Indian Himalayas., EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-702, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-702 .	No
7	Lombardi, A., Cerasoli, F., Tomassetti, B., Tuccella, P., Redaelli, G., Di Cicco, M., Fiasca, B., Di Sabatino, A., and Galassi, D. M. P. (2023): Preliminary assessment of the relationships between rainfall, flow discharge and biodiversity changes in a karst spring system in central Italy, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-12755, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-12755 .	No
8	Braeunig, L., Schloo, M., Burke, V., Greskowiak, J., and Massmann, G. (2023): Geochemical side effects of potential Managed Aquifer Recharge during infiltration of monovalent partial desalinated water into different dune sands, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-15634, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-15634 .	No

2.3.4. Orals Third Sub-Session: Groundwater Management

The last sub-session on groundwater management began with the presentation of the invited guest, Marx Andreas from UFZ, on “Development of a National-scale Decision Support System for the Water sector in Germany” and a total of 7 oral presentations, 3 under the InTheMED project.

Table 4. Summary of the orals third sub-session with references for the abstracts, highlighting the ones presented under the InTheMED project.

#	Oral Presentations	Under InTheMED Project?
1	Andreas, M., Friedrich, B., Christian, S., Rebekka, L., Thomas, S., Jan, B., Georg, T., and Sabine, A. (2023): Development of a national-scale decision support system for the water sector in Germany, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-7678, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-7678 .	No
2	Uygur, İ., Yoloğlu, O. C., Copty, N. K., Daloğlu Çetinkaya, İ., and Saysel, A. K. (2023): Partial validation of a socio-economic system dynamics model against a process based hydro-geological model, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-3417, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-3417 .	Yes
3	Yoloğlu, O. C., Uygur, İ., Copty, N. K., Daloğlu Çetinkaya, İ., and Saysel, A. K. (2023): Evaluation of Different Water Management Practices for the Sustainable Use of Groundwater Resources in the Konya Closed Basin, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-8796, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-8796 .	Yes
4	Rubio-Martin, A., Pulido-Velazquez, M., Lopez-Perez, E., Sanchis-Ibor, C., Garcia-Prats, A., Manzano-Juarez, J., Garcia-Molla, M., Jimenez-Bello, M. A., Peñalvo-Lopez, E., Rinaudo, J.-D., Faysse, N., Nieto-Romero, M., Bento, S., Nunes, L., Serrao de Sousa, V., Bouzidi, Z., and Nejari, A. (2023): IMPROVING GROUNDWATER MANAGEMENT IN THE MEDITERRANEAN REGION THROUGH CITIZEN SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY: THE eGROUNDWATER PROJECT, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-11715, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-11715 .	No
5	Anyfanti, I. V., Lyronis, A., Diakoparaskevas, P., Varouchakis, E., and Karatzas, G. P. (2023): Sustainable groundwater management using a combined simulation–optimization approach, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-5943, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-5943 .	Yes
6	Akrouf, H., Mellah, T., Mansouri, L., Baccouche, H., and Ghrabi, A.: Assessment of sustainable textile Wastewater Treatment for providing of non-conventional Water- resource related to other activities, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-3966, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-3966 .	Yes
7	Sánchez García, D., Argamasilla Ruiz, M., Palomino Gómez, A., Díaz Hurtado, M. Á., García Ortiz, L., Núñez Moreno, F., Nieto López, J. M., and Aguilera Romero, D. (2023): GTool: A new user-driven tool aiming at achieving a sustainable groundwater governance in Mediterranean aquifers, EGU General Assembly 2023, Vienna, Austria, 24–28 Apr 2023, EGU23-16409, https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-16409 .	No

3. Final remarks

The InTheMED final scientific conference was successfully organized and encompassed the participation of all partners of the project and other conference participants that attended the session. Each partner did an update about the work progress of each WP and an overview of the status and outcomes of the project. Moreover, during the session, each partner presented the technical work that has been developing under the InTheMED project framework.

There was also the opportunity for social activities to promote networking and collaboration opportunities under the project among the teams.

Annexes

Detailed agenda | April 28th, 2023

April 28th, 2023 @ 08:30 – 17:40 · EGU session HS8.1.9 “Sustainable Groundwater Management in Water Stressed Regions”

08:30 Posters on site and virtual

10:15 Coffee break

10:45 Orals | 5-minute convener introduction, Jaime Gómez-Hernández

“Machine learning, inverse modelling and geostatistics”

Chairpersons: Vanessa A. Godoy, George Karatzas

10:50 David Hyndman et al. | Solicited talk (invited guest) | Using remote sensing and integrated hydrology models to characterize the how irrigated agriculture affects highly overdrawn aquifers in the United States | EGU23-17218

11:10 Daniele Secci et al. | An artificial neural network as a quick tool to assess the effects of climate change and agricultural policies on groundwater resources | EGU23-5801

11:20 Yueting Li et al. | Surrogate-based Bayesian characterization of porous and deformable aquifer systems in water stressed regions | EGU23-8761

11:30 Amir Rouhani et al. | Impact of climate change on groundwater levels in the Iberian Peninsula | EGU23-12968

11:40 Janire Uribe-Asarta et al. | Random Forests-Based Surrogate Model as a Tool to Facilitate Groundwater Management | EGU23-13470

11:50 Madhusmita Ojha | Demarcation of lowered water table zones in a drought-affected area of western Odisha, India | EGU23-3742

12:00 Cláudia Escada and Leonardo Azevedo | Deep Direct Current Resistivity Inversion | EGU23-299

12:10 Leonardo Azevedo and João L. Pereira | Deep generative inversion of ERT data for electrical resistivity | EGU23-15753

12:20 Constantinos F. Panagiotou *et al.* | Assessment of groundwater quality and piezometric levels using geostatistical methods in Grombalia aquifer, Tunisia | EGU23-8037

12:30 Lunch

“Modelling”

Chairpersons: Maria Giovanna Tanda, Seifeddine Jomaa

14:00 Session introduction

14:05 James Butler | Extending aquifer lifespans with pumping reductions: Experiences from the High Plains aquifer | EGU23-9552

14:25 Marcus Genzel *et al.* | Regional-scale groundwater modeling, focusing on boundary inflow and impact assessment of managed aquifer recharge in karst systems | EGU23-16393

14:35 Cigdem Eryilmaz Saylan *et al.* | A Groundwater Flow Modeling Application for the Impact Assessment of Treated Wastewater Reuse by Managed Aquifer Recharge | EGU23-13121

14:45 Harald Klammler *et al.* | Simplified integrated modeling and potential groundwater management benefits of the unsaturated zone in the Urucuia aquifer system, Brazil | EGU23-4229

14:55 Yuvraj Patil and Amarsinh Landage | Evaluation of the Semi-Arid Region Groundwater Storage Potential for Solapur Region, Maharashtra, India | EGU23-4199

15:05 Bhargabnanda Dass and Sumit Sen | Understanding spring aquifer dynamics through observational data patterns, stable isotopes, and hydrochemistry – An account of experimental pilots in the Indian Himalayas | EGU23-702

15:15 Annalina Lombardi *et al.* | Preliminary assessment of the relationships between rainfall, flow discharge and biodiversity changes in a karst spring system in central Italy | EGU23-12755

15:25 Laura Braeunig *et al.* | Geochemical side effects of potential Managed Aquifer Recharge during infiltration of monovalent partial desalinated water into different dune sands | EGU23-15634

15:35 Coffee break

“Groundwater management”

Chairperson: Jaime Gómez-Hernández

16:15 Session introduction

16:20 Marx Andreas *et al.* | Development of a national-scale decision support system for the water sector in Germany | EGU23-7678

16:40 İzel Uygur *et al.* | Partial validation of a socio-economic system dynamics model against a process-based hydro-geological model | EGU23-3417

16:50 Onur Cem Yoloğlu *et al.* | Evaluation of Different Water Management Practices for the Sustainable Use of Groundwater Resources in the Konya Closed Basin | EGU23-8796

17:00 Adria Rubio-Martin *et al.* | Improving groundwater management in the Mediterranean region through citizen science and technology: the eGROUNDWATER project. | EGU23-11715

17:10 Ioanna V. Anyfanti *et al.* | Sustainable groundwater management using a combined simulation–optimization approach | EGU23-5943

17:20 Hanene Akrouf *et al.* | Assessment of sustainable textile Wastewater Treatment for providing of non-conventional Water- resource related to other activities | EGU23-3966

17:30 Damián Sánchez García *et al.* | GTool: A new user-driven tool aiming at achieving a sustainable groundwater governance in Mediterranean aquifers | EGU23-16409

17:40 Closure